

VASTLY INCREASED FILAMENT PRODUCT OUTPUT

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SUMMARY: This is a description of a machine that vastly increases the Kg rate per hour of fiber application per hour for the filament winding of pipe and for the fiber placement process. A fiber delivery system that consists of multiple pairs of crossing fiber bands having small wind angle differences places fibers around the periphery of a product. The machine configuration, motions and fiber paths are described. The volume output of fibers is tabulated and compared with contemporary systems.

KEYWORDS: Low Cost Production, Filament Winding, Winding Machines

INTRODUCTION

The increasing market for fiber composites is encouraging. Cost effectiveness and volume outputs for most filament wound products are far below that of metals. Cost reduction alone cannot increase market share or enter large volume markets such as pipe. There is need for production capacity beyond that now available. Vastly increased machine output significantly reduces labor content and floor space. Winding equipment not now available is needed to satisfy the large market for pipe now satisfied by metal.. Filament winding is highly automated. It uses fibers in their lowest cost form. Wound products have the highest fiber volume content and strength. Large products have the lowest labor content per product pound. Equipment for volume application of fibers for products is one of the essential elements for competing with metal.

MACHINE MOTIONS

The relative machine motions for the separate fiber dispensing systems are such that the bands have deposit angles differing in a range between 3° and 6° . For clarity, Fig. 1 depicts a portion only of the complete coverage band. In Fig. 2 angle +A is superimposed on +B angle band in the left to right band deposit because it's increased angle dictates that the band deposit be advanced over that of angle +A. In the right to left deposit the angle +A is now underneath because it's motion is slower. Fig. 3 shows the two motions such that the distance traveled by each dispensing system is identical for each circuit. The travel is equal from left to right plus return to the beginning. Fig. 4 depicts an eight fiber band radial dispensing system with independent motion for each pair of A and B angles. The ply thickness for this system per circuit is 16 times that of present winding and

placement full coverage one end to the other. The output increase is even greater because most present equipment uses less than full coverage fiber bands on products greater than 2.5cm diameter. For this system to perform correctly: First, the total fiber band delivery time from one end of the winding plus return to the other must be exactly the same for both angle delivery systems. Secondly, using the single desired angle π as the average, angles π_1 and π_2 are selected by determination of the angle difference possible without fiber distortion. Thirdly, the fiber bandwidth is such that there is complete coverage of the winding surface as the band is placed from one end to the other. Eqn 1.

$$\{1\} = \pi \times \text{wind diameter} \times \cos \text{wind angle} = \text{full coverage band width.}$$

Fig. 1: Simultaneous Band Positions

Fig. 2: Band Relative Position Change

FIBER PATHS

The separate fiber paths at each end of the winding are established by the radius of curvature of the 180° change in direction required for the headstock to tailstock and return to headstock motion of the fiber band delivery devices. The radius can be changed by the programming input or by a mechanical means. Each fiber path starts at the machine headstock end at the horizontal edge of this radius. The fiber path is at 90° orientation until the vertical position of the radius is reached. At this point, the path is a sine wave of the programmed angles that are a plus angle in this direction. Near the tailstock end, the fiber paths change from the programmed winding angles to that of 90° at the start of the turn around radius. The path remains at or close to 90° until it enters a sine wave motion of the minus programmed winding angle. This motion is constant for each angle until the fiber paths reach the radius turnaround at the headstock end of the machine. The paths of both fiber angles coincide at the headstock end. The few degrees of difference in the fiber band placement of the separate paths affect the fiber positions at the tailstock end. The lower angle windings arrive at the tailstock end before those of the high angle. The lower angle windings also start toward the headstock end before those of the high angle. The fiber path angles are reversed at the tailstock end to allow both paths to arrive exactly at identical positions at the headstock end. Wet winding is used instead of prepreg. The resin volume fraction can be changed throughout the wall of the product. This will overcome the usual migration of resin from the inside of the windings as the plys accumulate. The result is greater outer fiber effectiveness.

Fig. 3: Machine Motions

Fig. 4: Machine Multiple Fiber Deliveries

MACHINE OUTPUT

The machine output rate in Kg of material per labor hour depends upon the size of the product. The filament winding process places material at a rate based upon the number of simultaneous plys placed, the bandwidth and fiber dispensing rate. Fiber dispensing rate is constant for particular fibers, impregnation considerations, fiber delivery, and band forming and tension systems. The bandwidth is dependent on the winding angle and product diameter. For a given winding angle, the machine output rate then is directly proportional to the diameter and number of simultaneous plys being placed. Small diameter filament wound products have a limited quantity of simultaneous plys applied due to the limited physical space available for the pairs of delivery devices. The Kg per hour output therefore increases directly as product diameter and quantity of pairs of placed simultaneous plys. The output of the pairs of angled bands is great enough that reduced fiber speed can be programmed for improved fiber impregnation and reduced fiber damage. Table 1 shows the vast increase of the fiber output rate when the fiber bands can be placed in pairs simultaneously without distortion and at many dispensing points. The low fiber speed of 20m per minute in the sim. Plcmt, *simultaneous placement*, column exhibits an output five times that of fibers at 70m per minute rate of conventional machines.

Table 1: Product Output of Machines

Pipe Diam. cm	Fiber Band Width - cm $\pm 55^\circ$ fv .55 fiberglass	No. of 100Kg yield rovings delivered 0.25x5.5mm	<i>Sim. plcm</i> <i>Fiber Bands</i> <i>20m / Min.</i> <i>Kg / Hr.</i>	Fiber Band speed 20m / Min. Kg / Hr.	Fiber Band speed 40m / Min. Kg / Hr.	Fiber Band speed 70m / Min. Kg / Hr.
150	270	90	<i>75</i>	18.8	9.4	16.4
300	540	180	<i>150</i>	37.6	18.8	32.9
600	1080	360	<i>301</i>	75	37.6	66
1200	2160	720	<i>601</i>	150	75	132
2000	3600	1200	<i>1002</i>	250	125	219

CONCLUSIONS

Pairs of crossing fiber bands at small angle differences allow plies of unlimited quantities to be dispensed to a product simultaneously. Rate of product output compared with existing equipment is vastly increased. Floor space and labor costs are reduced. Due to the character of the filament winding and fiber placement, the machine output is proportional to the diameter and number of simultaneous plies being placed. As product diameters increase the cost reductions and rate of Kg output per hour is orders of magnitude greater for all wound items than that wound by existing equipment.

